

BMF CP82: Space tourism, information trustworthiness, usefulness, and immersiveness

AISDL Team

September 25, 2024

“Her delicate figure embodies the phrase “a swan’s grace,” yet she possesses incredible strength, easily lifting a three-ounce fish up to her branch. But most importantly, her ethereal attire earns her the title of “Dreamy Wings.” Her entire being is like an ethereal painting, a playful creation of nature using colors, lines, dots, strokes, and patches. One can only exclaim, “Absolutely enchanting. Is this real or an illusion?””

—In “The Philosophy of Awakening”; [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

[COLLABORATIVE PROJECT]

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How are information trustworthiness, usefulness, and immersiveness associated with the general intention to try space tourism?
- Does the uncertainty of information (proxied by information trustworthiness) moderate the associations between information usefulness, immersiveness, and the general intention to try space tourism?

1.2. Materials

The granular interaction thinking of mindsponge theory will be used for the conceptual development of this study, while Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be used for statistical analysis [1-4]. The dataset comprises 361 respondents through snowball and convenient sampling targeted to samples interested in space tourism [5]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the Bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [6]. For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/13834848>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis shows that information trustworthiness, usefulness, and immersiveness are positively associated with the general intention to try space tourism. However, the information trustworthiness is found to have a negative moderation effect on the associations between information usefulness, immersiveness, and the general intention to try space tourism (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Estimated coefficients

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps for registering to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**

AISDL members who have joined this project: Viet-Phuong La, Quan-Hoang Vuong.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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